

Hybridization of FDTD with Nested Shielded Multiconductor Transmission Lines and ngspice Interconnections

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Abstract—This article presents the hybridization of a 3D full-wave Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) solver with a multi-level multiconductor transmission line (MTL) solver, using the circuit simulator ngspice to treat network connections. This schema is intended to study the electromagnetic response of 3D systems where networks of shielded cables (wiring) are present. The MTL solver can simulate networks of shielded cable bundles with an arbitrary topology. Bundles interconnects and terminations are described using ngspice. Interaction between different levels in the bundle is described by means of the transfer impedance of the shields.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method [1], [2] is one of the most widely used methods in electromagnetic analysis. It is customarily used to analyze transient fields in a three-dimensional domain and to obtain the time-domain response of non-linear complex systems, such as the bulk structures of aircraft. FDTD is also used to obtain the time-domain response of wiring networks, modeled as one-dimensional multiconductor transmission lines (MTLs) [3]. However, the scale of the aeronautical and automotive system and of their wiring networks greatly differ. The time step of the FDTD method is proportional to the space step and if the space step is reduced enough to adequately describe the wires,

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the time step will decrease accordingly, leading to extremely long simulation times. There are some methods to include sub-cell structures in FDTD without reducing the space step [4]–[8]. However, none can handle all the characteristics of multiconductor networks: large number of nested, multiconductor cable bundles, and complex connections between bundles and between bundles and structures.

In MTL solvers using FDTD the connections and terminations of MTLs are usually limited to resistive elements [9] and to combinations of nonlinear elements [10]–[12]. In the latter the implementation depends on the particular connection topology not being possible to generalize them to describe arbitrary connections between bundles. Dispersive elements can be included [13] adding auxiliary equations. The simulation of interconnections where electronic components are present is not possible in any of the methods above.

In this paper we propose the hybridization of a state-of-the-art open-source 3D full-wave FDTD solver [14] with a comprehensive MTL solver with interconnections managed by a circuit solver. The MTL solver can simulate networks of shielded cable bundles. Each shielded MTL can have an arbitrary number of nested levels. The system can be excited by internal sources and/or external plane waves. The coupling of the shields with the conductors therein is described using a bidirectional transfer impedance. The interconnections and the terminations of the MTL are treated using a spice simulator of electric and electronic circuits, ngspice [15].

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The coupling of a shielded cable bundle with an external electromagnetic field can be studied regarding the bundle as a shielded MTL in which the outer shield interacts with the external field. The rest of the bundle, internal to the shield, is coupled to the shield through its transfer impedance and admittance. To include the cable described using the MTL formalism in the full-wave domain in which the field

propagation is studied both set of equations have to be coupled. The cable is introduced as an element in the full-wave domain, and discretized along the grid used in the FDTD method, each section of the cable belonging to a cell of the grid. Inside each FDTD cell a TEM approximation is assumed. Considering a shielded MTL with n conductors surrounded by a shield inside a field domain, the set of equations that describes the interaction between the fields and the transmission line is:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\mu \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}}{\partial t} \quad (1a)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \varepsilon \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} + \sigma \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J}_s \quad (1b)$$

$$\partial_z \{\mathbf{V}\} = -[\mathbf{L}] \partial_t \{\mathbf{I}\} - [\mathbf{R}] \{\mathbf{I}\} + [\mathbf{Z}] * \{\mathbf{I}\} + \{\mathbf{E}_T\} \quad (1c)$$

$$\partial_z \{\mathbf{I}\} = -[\mathbf{C}] \partial_t \{\mathbf{V}\} - [\mathbf{G}] \{\mathbf{V}\} + [\mathbf{Y}] * \{\mathbf{V}\} \quad (1d)$$

where $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}(x, y, z, t)$ and $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}(x, y, z, t)$ are the electric and magnetic vector fields, $\mathbf{J}_s = \mathbf{J}_s(x, y, z, t)$ is the source current density and μ , ε and σ are, respectively, the permeability, permittivity and conductivity of the medium outside the MTL. $[\mathbf{L}]$ and $[\mathbf{C}]$ are the per-unit-length inductance and capacitance between all conductors and $[\mathbf{R}]$ and $[\mathbf{G}]$ are the per-unit-length losses: resistance (along conductors) and conductance (between conductors). $\{\mathbf{V}\}(z, t) = [V_1 V_2 \dots V_{n+1}]^T$, where V_1 is the in-cell voltage of the outermost shield (the voltage with respect to the cell boundary) and V_i with $i \in \{2, \dots, n+1\}$ are the voltages of the rest of the conductors with respect to their closest outer shield. $\{\mathbf{I}\}(z, t) = [I_1 I_2 \dots I_{n+1}]^T$ is the vector of currents on those conductors. $[\mathbf{Z}]$ and $[\mathbf{Y}]$ are, respectively, the shield transfer impedance and admittance. These are frequency dependent quantities and the $*$ operator indicates that these terms are time-domain convolutions of frequency dependent quantities. $\{\mathbf{E}_T\}(z, t) = [E_T, 1, 0 \dots 0]$ is the vector of external tangential fields. Only the external shield is subject to the direct influence of the field, hence only the first component is non-zero. We will assume that the lines are uniform and homogeneous, and that their per-unit-length properties are frequency independent. The coupling between the full-wave and the MTL schemas is mediated by the interaction between (1b) and (1c) through the electric field and current terms.

A. Cable bundles

For a shielded cable bundle with m levels of conductors, there will be m equations as (1c) and (1d), one for each level. Each level is potentially coupled to the level above and the level below through the transfer impedance and admittance describing the shields. The transfer impedance describes the voltage that appears inside an imperfect shield when a current circulates through it, whereas the transfer admittance describes the current that appears on the inside a the shield that has a voltage difference with respect to its reference [16]. Except for very large braid apertures [17], [18] or large termination impedances of the external line [16] the contribution of the admittance can be neglected. We will consider that the coupling in the shields is bidirectional. The transfer impedance matrix is a block matrix where the only non-zero components

are those Z_{ij} and Z_{ji} such that j correspond to the conductors shielded by conductor i .

Regarding the per-unit-length parameters, L_1 and C_1 are, respectively, the *in-cell* inductance and capacitance which, following [4], [6], can be computed as:

$$L_1 = \frac{\mu}{2\pi} \frac{\int \int_{\Delta y \Delta z, r > r_{sh}} \ln(r/r_{sh}) dy dz}{\int \int_{\Delta y \Delta z, r > r_{sh}} dy dz} \quad (2a)$$

$$C_1 = \mu \varepsilon / L_1 \quad (2b)$$

where r_{sh} is the radius of the external shield of the bundle, Δx and Δy are the spatial steps transversal to the direction of the bundle, and μ and ε are the permeability and permittivity of the medium surrounding the cable. $[L]_j$ and $[C]_j$, with $j \in \{2, \dots, m\}$, are the inductance and capacitance of each level with respect to the shield corresponding to such level. These can be computed using the theoretical expressions for shielded multiconductors [3] or using an electrostatic solver [19], taking the outer shield as the reference conductor.

Due to the cross-coupling between levels created by the bidirectional transfer impedance the m equations stemming from (1c) and (1d) cannot be solved independently for the TL that represents each level, and all levels have to be solved as a single matrix equation.

B. Discretization

The equations in (1) are discretized using the FDTD method described in [3]. The $[\mathbf{Z}] * \{\mathbf{I}\}$ term represents the time-domain convolution of a frequency dependent transfer impedance with a current vector. Following [13], [20], if $[\mathbf{Z}]$ is substituted by a rational approximation the Piecewise Linear Recursive Formulations (PRLC) can be used to express the convolution in the time domain. If the frequency-dependent transfer impedance is approximated by a rational approximation, the convolution term can be written as:

$$[\mathbf{Z}] * \{\mathbf{I}\} = [\mathbf{d}] \mathbf{I} + [\mathbf{c}] \partial_t \mathbf{I} + \sum_i [r]_i \int_0^t e^{[p]_i (t-\tau)} \mathbf{I}(z, t-\tau) d\tau \quad (3)$$

where $[\mathbf{d}]$, $[\mathbf{e}]$, $[\mathbf{r}]$ and $[\mathbf{p}]$ are the matrices of terms of the rational approximation. If (3) is discretized, the summation term takes the form

$$\sum_i [r]_i \int_0^t e^{[p]_i (t-\tau)} \{\mathbf{I}\}(z, t-\tau) = \sum_i [\varphi]_i^n \quad (4)$$

with

$$[\varphi]_i^n = [q_1]_i \{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n+3/2} + [q_2]_i \{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n+1/2} + [q_3]_i [\varphi]_i^n$$

Details of the implementation of the method and the derivation of the terms $[\varphi]$, $[q_1]$, $[q_2]$ and $[q_3]$ can be found in [21], where it was implemented to describe frequency dependent lumped impedances.

The final discretized field, voltage and current equations are:

$$\mathbf{H}^{n+1} = \mathbf{H}^n - \frac{\delta t}{\mu} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}^{n+1/2} \quad (5a)$$

$$\mathbf{E}^{n+3/2} = \frac{\varepsilon - \sigma \Delta t/2}{\varepsilon + \sigma \Delta t/2} \mathbf{E}^{n+1/2} + \frac{\Delta t}{\varepsilon + \sigma \Delta t/2} (\nabla \times \mathbf{H}^{n+1} - \mathbf{J}_k^{n+1}) \quad (5b)$$

$$\{\mathbf{V}\}_k^{n+1} = F_{V\pm}^{-1} [F_{V-} \{\mathbf{V}\}_k^n - (\{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n+1/2} - \{\mathbf{I}\}_{k-1}^{n+1/2})] \quad (5c)$$

$$\{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n+3/2} = F_{I\pm}^{-1} \left[F_{I-} \{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n+1/2} - (\{\mathbf{V}\}_{k+1}^{n+1} - \{\mathbf{V}\}_{k+1}^n) + E_T - \Delta z \sum_i [q_{3i}]_i [\varphi]_i^{n-1} \right] \quad (5d)$$

where

$$F_{V\pm} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [C] \pm \frac{\Delta z}{2} [G] \right) \quad (6a)$$

$$F_{I+} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [L] + \frac{\Delta z}{2} [R] + \frac{\Delta z}{2} [d] + \frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [e] + \Delta z \sum_i [q_{1i}]_i \right) \quad (6b)$$

$$F_{I-} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [L] - \frac{\Delta z}{2} [R] - \frac{\Delta z}{2} [d] + \frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [e] - \Delta z \sum_i [q_{2i}]_i \right) \quad (6c)$$

C. Terminations and interconnections

The equations above describe a shielded cable bundle but not the elements on its extremes. The problem in incorporating the terminal conditions in FDTD is that the voltages and currents of the line are not collocated neither in space or time, whereas the terminal conditions relate the current and voltage at the same point and the same time.

We will use the circuit solver ngspice to treat the terminations of the MTLs. Since ngspice is a circuit solver, we will try to find a circuit equivalent for the transmission line. If we take the discretized transmission line shown in Fig. 1a and apply the FDTD scheme to (1d) at the extremes of the line (source and load, respectively), we can find update relations for the current at the source and the load can be derived:

$$I_S^{n+1/2} = I_1^{n+1/2} + C \frac{\Delta z}{2} \partial_t V_1^{n+1/2} + G \frac{\Delta z}{2} V_1^{n+1/2} \quad (7a)$$

$$I_L^{n+1/2} = I_N^{n+1/2} - C \frac{\Delta z}{2} \partial_t V_{N+1}^{n+1/2} - G \frac{\Delta z}{2} V_{N+1}^{n+1/2} \quad (7b)$$

(7a) and (7b) represent each a node equation with four currents: the current at the source (load), the current of the first (last) segment of the transmission line, the current $I' = \frac{1}{2} C \Delta z \partial_t V$ through a capacitor with value $C' = \frac{1}{2} C \Delta z$ and the current $I'' = \frac{1}{2} G \Delta z V$ through a resistor with value $R = (\frac{1}{2} G \Delta z)^{-1}$ [22]. From the point of view of ngspice, the extremes of the transmission line are equivalent to these circuits. We can exploit the circuit equivalent of the extreme of the transmission line to use ngspice to perform the update of the voltage in the extremes of the line (V_1 and V_{N+1}). A

circuit is defined in ngspice using a netlist describing the terminations of the transmission line, i.e representing the *source* and *load* in Fig. 1a. The ngspice circuit of each termination is connected to a circuit representing the corresponding end of the transmission line, as in Fig. 1b, where \hat{I}_i, \hat{V}_j (with $i = 1, N, j = 1, N + 1$) represent the currents and voltages at the extremes of the transmission line. A transient analysis is defined to have the same beginning and end, and the same time step as the MTL FDTD simulation.

(a) Discretized transmission line showing source and load currents, collocated in time and space with the voltages at the extremes of the line.

(b) Equivalent circuit of the extreme of a transmission line.

Fig. 1. Construction of the circuit model of the extremes of the transmission line.

D. Algorithm

With the discretization of the field equations and the MTL equations in (5), and the procedure to use ngspice to advance the voltage of the extremes of the MTLs, a combined FDTD solution can be constructed. The iterative procedure to update fields, currents and voltages is:

- 1) advance the voltage of each TL at all nodes except those on the extremes $\{\mathbf{V}\}_k^{n+1}$ ($k = 2 \dots N$) using (5c);
- 2) advance the voltage on the extremes of each TL $\{\mathbf{V}\}_1^{n+1}$ and $\{\mathbf{V}\}_{N+1}^{n+1}$, advancing all ngspice circuits:
 - for each TL attached to a junction, update the corresponding current source $\hat{I}_{i,k}$, using the current of the transmission line segment attached to that node, $I_{i,k}^{n+1/2}$, with $k = 1, k = N$, and i corresponding to the TL;
 - advance the transient ngspice simulation by Δt ;
 - assign each $\hat{V}_{i,k}$ to the corresponding voltage on the TL $V_{i,k}^{n+1}$ ($k = 1$ or $k = N$).
- 3) advance the current of each TL $\{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n+3/2}$ ($k = 1 \dots N$) using (5d);
- 4) advance the electric field $\mathbf{E}^{n+3/2}$ using (5b) and $\mathbf{J}^{n+3/2} = I^{n+3/2} \cdot S^{-1} \mathbf{k}$, where $S = \Delta i \Delta j$ is the cell area transversal to direction \mathbf{k} , the direction of \mathbf{E} .
- 5) advance the magnetic field \mathbf{H}^{n+1} using (5a)

III. VALIDATION

The proposed hybridized solver is validated comparing simulations with measurements performed at the laboratory of the GCEM-UPC [23]. The validation uses two different methods: a plane wave incident on a shielded wire using a *EUROTEM* TEM cell [24] (Sec. III-B) and a wire panel, where we measure the cross-talk in a two-conductor transmission line between the excited line and the receptor line, terminated with an op-amp (Sec. III-C).

A. Code implementation

The full-wave FDTD solver and the MTL solver are written in Fortran and are part of a state-of-the-art general-purpose time-domain simulator developed and validated by the GEG team [25] for various applications [21], [26], [27]. Ngspice is an open-source spice simulator for electric and electronic circuits in which PSPICE or LTSPICE device model parameters and netlists can be used for simulating discrete circuits [15].

B. Validation with a TEM cell

1) *Measurement setup*: The TEM cell consists of four stripline antennas housed inside an absorbent-lined enclosure (Fig. 2a) According to the manufacturer, inside the cell there is a volume of $20 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ cm}^3$ in which the field can be assumed to be a plane wave. The antennas can be excited to propagate vertically- or horizontally-polarized TEM waves, the direction of propagation being the longest dimension of the cell.

To test the plane wave assumption we have measured the electric field intensity at the position where the wire will be positioned using an electric field probe *FL7006* [28]. According to the manufacturer, this has an uncertainty of $\pm 0.8 \text{ dB}$ in the frequency range 0.1 GHz to 1 GHz . The function generator is a *HAMEG 8134* [29]. The wire will be aligned in the y direction, and the deviation from the plane wave assumption should not be relevant as long as the field along the wire remains constant. We have measured the field in the x , y and z directions at the positions corresponding to the extremes of the wire (Tab. I). For each direction, each value indicates the field measured at each extreme. The difference between the fields measured at the extremes of the wire for the y direction is negligible. For the purposes of replicating the experimental setup in the simulation we can consider that we are using a plane wave. For the validation using the shielded wire we need the field intensity to be higher. Otherwise, the field inside the coaxial will be below the sensitivity of our instruments. We have amplified the voltage of the function generator using a *B1080M-10* amplifier. The field measured can be seen in Tab. I. We have assumed that the homogeneity of the field along the wire still holds, and have measured the field only at one position of the wire.

2) *Shielded wire excited by plane wave*: We use the TEM cell to excite a coaxial cable. The cable enters the cell along the direction of propagation of the plane wave through a metallic cylinder in ohmic contact with the enclosure. At the center of the volume where the excitation can be considered a plane wave a segment of 7 cm is bent into the vertical

TABLE I
FIELD VALUES MEASURED WITH THE FIELD PROBE *FL7006* FOR TWO DIFFERENT INPUT POWERS, CORRESPONDING TO THE UNAMPLIFIED AND AMPLIFIED SIGNALS

input [dBm]	E_x [V/m]		E_y [V/m]		E_z [V/m]	
13	0.025	0.024	1.859	1.890	0.212	0.429
39	5.60		42.29		5.26	

(a) Outside view of the chamber

(b) Geometry of the simulation setup

Fig. 2. TEM cell: outside view and geometry of the simulation setup

position. We use a vertically polarized plane wave. Thus, only the vertical segment of the cable should be excited by the wave. The *BNC* connector of the extreme of the cable inside the cell has been removed and has been terminated on a 50Ω resistor connecting the shield and the inner wire. The rest of the cable has been left intact.

According to the manufacturer, the transfer impedance of the coaxial cable can be modeled as $Z_T(\omega) = R_T + j\omega L_T$, with $R_T = 0.01 \Omega \text{ m}^{-1}$ and $L_T = 10 \text{ nH m}^{-1}$. This value is extremely sensitive to the manufacturing process and to the proper use and storage of the cable. According to [30], the uncertainty in the transfer impedance can be as high as 25%. The shielded conductor is modeled as a nested transmission line with two levels and two conductors, one corresponding to the shield and the other corresponding to the inner wire. A vertically polarized plane wave is injected equal to $E(t) = E_0 \cdot \sin(2\pi f t)$, with $E_0 = 42.29 \text{ V}$ (Tab. I) and $f = 550 \text{ kHz}$. The frequency is chosen in a frequency

range where the suppression of the longitudinal and transversal field components is maximal according to the manufacturer of the TEM cell. The simulation runs for 20 ns with a time step $\Delta t = 2.5$ fs

Fig. 3 shows the voltage between the inner conductor and the shield, measured at the wire end, comparing the simulation to the measured results. The uncertainty in the measurement corresponds to the uncertainty of the oscilloscope used, a *Rhode & Schwarz RTC1002* [31]: 3% of the reading + 0.1 div + 1 mV, in the scale 1 mV/div. To account for the uncertainty in the simulation we have repeated the simulation varying the shield transfer impedance by a $\pm 25\%$ the field intensity by a ± 0.8 dB. The uncertainty in the simulation corresponds to sum in quadrature of the uncertainties obtained in each case.

Fig. 3. Voltage between the inner conductor and the shield of a shielded wire, induced by an incident plane wave.

C. Validation with the wire panel

1) *Measurement setup*: The measurement setup consists on an aluminum sheet with two L-shaped profiles. Two wires connect the two profiles, attached to *N*-type ports (Fig. 4). The wires are 40 cm long, are separated 10 cm and lay 4 cm above the ground plane. Losses in the wires are considered to be negligible, and the per-unit-length inductance and capacitance matrices, referred to the sheet below them, are:

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} 938.95 & 39.87 \\ 39.87 & 938.95 \end{bmatrix} \text{ nH} \quad C = \begin{bmatrix} 11.87 & -0.504 \\ -0.504 & 11.87 \end{bmatrix} \text{ pF} \quad (8)$$

These values have been computed using a dedicated electrostatic solver, and their values match those of the theoretical expressions for two wires over a ground plane [32]. The signal generator used was a *Agilent 33220A* [33] and for data acquisition a *Rhode & Schwarz RTC1002* oscilloscope was used [31].

2) *Cross-talk*: Measuring cross-talk in multiconductor transmission lines is one of the features customarily present in TL solvers. However, the interferences caused in an electronic component due to the signal carried by a nearby wire is a novelty incorporated thanks to the coupling with ngspice. To validate this situation we have used the setup shown in Fig. III-C1. A two conductor line is excited with a source

Fig. 4. View of the wire panel

Fig. 5. Two-conductor line. One wire is connected to the source and acts as the interference generator. The receptor wire is terminated with an op-amp

on the extreme of one of the wires, and the output voltage of an op-amp attached to the other wire is measured. In this case two different excitation signals were used. A sinusoidal signal and a pulse train, to have a case more representative of signals in digital systems. Since the induced voltages are proportional to the amplitude and the frequency of the source signal, the excitation had a frequency of $f = 1$ MHz and an amplitude of $V_{pp} = 20$ V in order to achieve a measurable cross-talk. With the signals used in the previous sections the op-amp output voltage would have been below the sensitivity of our instruments. In the case of the pulse train, the pulses had a rise time, fall time, duration and frequency of $\tau_r = 75$ ns, $\tau_f = 75$ ns, $\tau_d = 250$ ns, and $f = 1$ MHz respectively. Fig. 6 shows the output voltages of op-amp, compared to measured data.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a FDTD hybridization of a 3D full-wave solver with a MTL solver to treat networks of cable bundles whose interconnections are treated using the circuit simulator ngspice. The MTL can simulate shielded cable bundles of arbitrary topology, with bidirectional shields, allowing to study both the emission and the susceptibility of realistic cable networks in complex electromagnetic environments. Using a circuit simulator to treat the connections in the network allows to simulate connections where non-linear and electronic components are present.

The method has been validated comparing with two laboratory setups that comprehensively test the features and integration levels of the hybridized solver, with very good agreement between the simulations and the measurements.

(a) op-amp output voltage with line excited with a sinusoidal signal.

(b) op-amp output voltage with line excited with a pulse wave.

Fig. 6. Effect of cross-talk from a line excited with a sinusoidal or a pulse signal on a line terminated on a Texas Instruments TL071cp operational amplifier [34].

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